

The Collection of the Shī'ite *Tafsīrs* by Ahl al-Bayt Institute, Irān (?)

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The program *Jame'* (*Jāmi'*, "anthology" "compilation") includes 59 "collections" (*majmū'āt*) of Shī'ite commentaries on the Qur'ān (*tafsīr*), consisting all in all of 538 volumes and totalling some 250,000 pages. Within this compilation, 26 "collections" (272 volumes) are in Persian and 33 "collections" (266 volumes) are in Arabic. The chronological frameworks of the *tafsīr* "collections" extend from the 3rd/9th to the 14th/20th centuries (inclusive). All the *tafsīrs* are introduced with necessary data such as the author's full name and date of death; the commentary's full and abbreviated name; place, publisher and year of the edition; number of volumes and pages.

The program includes a complete text of the Qur'ān, together with a recitation (*tartīl*) of all the āyas (verses) and sūras (chapters) as performed by a professional reciter, Shahriyār Parhīzkār.

In addition, the program includes eighteen translations of the Qur'ān into Persian, by various translators, and one English translation, that of Marmaduke Pickthall. Each translation is provided with brief bibliographical indications of the translator's full name, the place and year of publication (except for the first three translations), and the number of pages. However, there is no indication of when the translators lived. The first three translations (in chronological order, but possibly according to the order of their being written down) are those of Ṣāhib Muḥaddith Dihlavī, al-Sayyid Riḍā al-Sarrāj, and Fayḍ al-Islām. A considerable portion of the translations were published in the late 20th century. Last to be published were the translations of Abū l-Ḥasan Sha'rānī (Tehran, 1374 shamsī/1995) and Bahā' al-Dīn Khurramshāh (Tehran, 1375 shamsī/1996).

The disk is accompanied by instructions for the user, in Persian, Arabic and English. These provide an outline of the contents of the disk, the general character of the program, and some of its particularities. Fortunately, the reader's esthetic enjoyment is enhanced by a choice from among twelve different calligraphic styles, some of them based on traditional Arabic scripts (*khatt*) such as *kūfī*, *naskh*, *thulth*, and so on.

With regard to the first Qur'ānic commentaries in Persian included in *Jame'*, the earliest of these is a unique example of a Persian commentary going back to the 6th/12th century, the *Rawḍ al-jinān wa-rawḥ al-janān* (= *Tafsīr Abī l-Futūḥ al-Rāzī*). The author is Ḥusayn b. 'Alī al-Khuzā'ī al-Nīshāpūrī (d. 552/1157). The edition contained in *Jame'* is a first edition (Mashhad, 1366-1374 shamsī/1987-1995) with 6,346 pp.; publication is (or was) ongoing. Then come five multivolume commentaries (from four to ten volumes each) from the second half of the 9th/15th until the 11th/17th centuries, composed by al-Ḥusayn b. al-Ḥasan Abū l-Maḥāsīn al-Jurjānī (end of the 9th/15th century), the *Jilā' al-adhhān wa-jalā' al-aḥzān*; Kamāl al-Dīn Ḥusayn Wā'iz al-Kashānī (d. 910/1504), the *Tafsīr al-Ḥusayn*; Mullā Faḥallāh al-Kashānī (d. between 977/1569 and 988/1580), the *Tafsīr manhaj al-ṣādiqīn fī ilzām al-mukhālifīn* and *Tafsīr khulāṣat al-Manhaj*; and Bahā' al-Dīn Muḥammad al-Lahījī (d. 1088/1677), *Tafsīr al-Sharīf Lahījī*.

For the following two centuries (the 12th/17th and 13th/19th), *Jame'* does not include a single Persian-language commentary, so far as we can tell from the indications of the authors' dates of death. By far the greatest number of Persian commentaries date from the 14th/20th century, but among these only five entries give indications of their authors' dates of death. These include the six-volume work of Sayyid Maḥmūd al-Tālaqānī (d. 1358 shamsī/1979), *Partavhā'ī az Qur'ān* (Tehran, 1358-1366 shamsī/1979-1987); the ten-volume commentary of Amīn Iṣfahānī (d. 1404/1983), *Makhzan al-'irfān dar 'ulūm al-Qur'ān*, or *Kanz al-'irfān* (Tehran, 1361 shamsī/1982); and others. Among these modern authors and compilers there are several major figures in contemporary religion and politics, in particular 'Alī Akbar Hāshimī Rafsanjānī, author of a commentary (Qom, 1373-1375 shamsī/1994-1996, six vols., 3,546 pp., publication ongoing).

The following is a complete list of the Shī'ī exegetical works in Arabic included in *Jame'*.

- 1) *Tafsīr al-Imām al-Ḥasan al-‘Askarī*, a commentary ascribed to the eleventh Imam al-Ḥasan b. ‘Alī Abū Muḥammad al-‘Askarī, who died in Samarra in 259/873-4. 1st ed., Qom, 1409/1988, 1 vol., 746 pp.
- 2) *Tafsīr al-Ḥibrī*, composed by al-Ḥusayn b. al-Ḥakam b. Muslim Abū ‘Abd Allāh al-Kūfī al-Ḥibrī (d. 286/899). 1st ed., Beirut, 1408/1987, 1 vol., 696 pp.
- 3) *Tafsīr Furāt al-Kūfī*, by Furāt b. Ibrāhīm b. Furāt Abū l-Qāsim al-Kūfī (an authority of the time of the “lesser occultation,” i.e. from 260/874 to 329/940). 1st ed., Tehran, 1410/1989, 1 vol., 720 pp.
- 4) *Tafsīr al-Qummī*, by ‘Alī b. Ibrāhīm b. Hāshim al-Qummī (d. ca. 307/919). 3rd ed., Qom, n.d., 2 vols., 880 pp.
- 5) *Tafsīr al-‘Ayyāshī*, by Muḥammad b. Mas‘ūd b. ‘Ayyāsh Abū l-Nadr al-Sulamī al-Samarqandī, known as al-‘Ayyāshī (d. 320/932). Tehran, n.d., 2 vols., 778 pp.
- 6) *al-Tibyān fī tafsīr al-Qur’ān (Tafsīr al-tibyān)*, by Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan b. ‘Alī Abū Ja‘far al-Ṭūsī (d. 460/1067). 1st ed., Qom, 1409/1988 (offset from the Beirut ed.), 10 vols., 5805 pp.
- 7) *Majma‘ al-bayān fī tafsīr al-Qur’ān*, by al-Faḍl b. al-Ḥasan Amīn al-Dīn Abū ‘Alī al-Ṭabarsī (d. 548/1153). Beirut, 1379/1959, 10 books in 5 vols., 2,818 pp. A translation of this tafsīr into Persian, provided by nine Iranian scholars, appears in the list of Shī‘ī commentaries in Persian included in *Jame‘*.
- 8) *Tafsīr jawāmi‘ al-jāmi‘*, also by al-Ṭabarsī (see previous). 3rd ed., Tehran, 1412/1991, 3 vols., 1724 pp. (carried over from the Beirut ed.).
- 9) *al-Muntakhab min tafsīr al-Qur’ān wal-nuqaṭ al-mustakhraja min Kitāb al-tibyān (= Muntakhab al-Tibyān)*, by Shaykh Muḥammad b. Aḥmad b. Idrīs Abū ‘Abd Allāh al-Ḥillī (d. 598/1202). 1st ed., Qom, 1409/1988, 2 vols., 832 pp.
- 10) *Nahj al-bayān ‘an kashf ma‘ānī al-Qur’ān*, by Muḥammad b. al-Ḥasan al-Shaybānī, a well-known scholar of the 7th/13th century. 1st ed., Tehran, 1413/1992, 1 vol., 394 pp., publication ongoing.

- 11) *Tafsīr Ṣadr al-Muta'allihīn (Tafsīr al-Qur'ān al-karīm)*, by Ṣadr al-Muta'allihīn Muḥammad b. Ibrāhīm Ṣadr al-Dīn al-Shīrāzī (d. 1050/1640). 2nd ed., Qom, 1366 shamsi/1987, 7 vols., 3,578 pp.
- 12) *al-Ṣāfi fī tafsīr kalām Allāh (= Tafsīr al-Ṣāfi)*, by al-Mawlā Muḥsin, known as al-Fayḍ al-Kāshānī (d. 1091/1680). 1st ed., Mashhad, n.d., 5 vols, 2,232 pp.
- 13) *al-Burhān fī tafsīr al-Qur'ān*, by al-Sayyid Hāshim al-Ḥusayn al-Baḥrānī (d. 1107/1696). 1st ed., Tehran, 1415/1994, 2 vols, 1,724 pp. (publication ongoing, toward an eventual total of four volumes).
- 14) *Tafsīr nūr al-thaqalayn* by al-Shaykh 'Abd 'Alī b. Jum'a al-'Alūsī al-Huvaysī (d. 1112/1700). 2nd ed., Qom, n.d., 5 vols., 3,401 pp.
- 15) *Tafsīr al-ma'īn*, by al-Mawlā Muḥammad b. al-Murtaḍā Nūr al-Dīn al-Kāshānī (d. after 1115/1703). 1st ed., Qom, 3 vols., 1,808 pp.
- 16) *al-Wajīz fī tafsīr al-Qur'ān al-'azīz (= al-Wajīz)*, by 'Alī b. al-Ḥusayn b. Abī Jāmi' al-'Āmilī (d. 1135/1722). 1st ed., Qom, 1413/1992, 1 vol., 528 pp., with publication ongoing.
- 17) *Tafsīr kanz al-daqā'iq wa-baḥr al-gharā'ib*, by Shaykh Muḥammad b. Muḥammad Riḍā al-Qummī al-Mashhadī (12th/18th century). 1st ed., Tehran, 1366 shamsī/1987, 14 vols., 7,606 pp.
- 18) *al-Jawhar al-samīn fī tafsīr al-kitāb al-mubīn*, by al-Sayyid 'Abd Allāh Shibr (d. 1242/1826). 1st ed., Kuwait, 1407/1986, 6 vols., 2,456 pp.
- 19) *Tafsīr al-Qur'ān al-karīm (= Tafsīr Shibr)*, by the same author as in the previous entry. 1st ed, Beirut, 1412/1991, 1 vol., 613 pp.
- 20) *Bayān al-sāda fī maqāmāt al-'ibāda*, by al-Ḥājj Sulṭān Muḥammad al-Janābāzī , known as Sulṭān 'Ali-shāh (d. 1327/1909). 2nd ed., Tehran, 1344 shamsī/1965, 4 vols., 1,450 pp.
- 21) *Muqtanayāt al-durar wa-multaqaṭāt al-samar*, by Mīr-sayyid al-Ḥā'irī al-Tehrānī (d. 1340/1921). Tehran, 1337 shamsī/1958, 12 vols., ca. 4,000 pp.

- 22) *Tafsīr al-Qur'ān al-karīm*, by Sayyid Muṣṭafā al-Khumaynī (d. 1397/1977). Tehran, 1362 shamsī/1983, 4 vols., 1,866 pp.
- 23) *al-Mīzān fī tafsīr al-Qur'ān (tafsīr al-mīzān)*, by al-Sayyid Muḥammad-Ḥusayn al-Ṭabāṭabā'ī (d. 1402/1981). 3rd ed., Tehran, 1397/1977, 20 vols, 8,764 pp. A Persian translation of this work was prepared by Sayyid Muḥammad-Bāqir al-Mūsāwī al-Hamadhānī, and published in Qom in 1363 shamsi/1984, 20 vols., 12,327 pp. This translation is also included in *Jame'*.
- 24) *Taqrīb al-Qur'ān ilā al-adhhān*, by Muḥammad b. al-Ḥusayn al-Shīrāzī (date of death unknown). 1st ed., Beirut, 1400/1980, 30 books (*jild*) in 10 vols., 4,698 pp.
- 25) *Tafsīr al-kāshif*, by Muḥammad Jawād Mughniyya (d. 1400/1980). 3rd ed., Beirut, 1981, 7 vols., 3,844 pp.
- 26) *al-Jadīd fī tafsīr al-Qur'ān*, by al-Shaykh Muḥammad al-Sabzavarī al-Najafī (d. 1410/1989). 1st ed., Beirut, 1402/1981, 7 vols., 3,585 pp.

The last seven of these 33 *tafsīrs* in Arabic are evidently the work of authors active in the late 20th century. For the most part, however, no dates of death are indicated for them. Thus we have:

- 27) *Min waḥy al-Qur'ān*, by Muḥammad Ḥusayn Faḍl Allāh. 3rd ed., Beirut, n.d., 25 books (*jild*) in 11 vols., 8,431 pp.
- 28) *al-Tafsīr li-kitāb Allāh al-munīr*, by Muḥammad al-Karāmī. Qom, 1402/1981, 7 vols., 2,726 pp.
- 29) *al-Amthal fī tafsīr kitāb Allāh al-munzal*, by Nāṣir Mukārim al-Shīrāzī. 1st ed., Beirut, 1413/1992, 20 vols., 10,516 pp.
- 30) *Mawāhib al-Raḥmān fī tafsīr al-Qur'ān*, by al-Sayyid 'Abd al-A'lā al-Mūsāwī al-Sabzavarī. Najaf, 1404/1983, 4 vols., 1,932 pp.
- 31) *Min hudā al-Qur'ān*, by al-Sayyid Muḥammad-taqī al-Mudarrisī. 1st ed., Dār al-Hudā, 1406/1985, 18 vols., 8,920 pp.
- 32) *Mukhtaṣar majma' al-bayān fī tafsīr al-Qur'ān*, by Shaykh Muḥammad-Bāqir al-Nāṣirī. 2nd ed., Qom, 1413/1992, 3 vols., 1,814 pp.

33) *Tafsīr al-baṣā'ir*, by Yaṣūb al-Dīn Rustaghār Jū'ibārī . Qom, 1399/1979-1413/1992.

This list testifies to the intensive activity that has gone on through the last two decades of the twentieth century down to the present day, regarding the publication of Shī'ī exegetical works in Arabic. Many of the recently-published works included in *Jame'* are first editions. Especially remarkable is the size of these exegetical works, including those that have been produced by contemporary authors. For sheer number of publications, pride of place must go to Qom, one of Iran's major religious centers.

The list also shows that the tradition of composing Qur'ānic commentaries in Arabic—the language of the sacred Muslim scriptures—has been carried on until the present day. This tradition was interrupted for a while, from the 8th/14th until the first half of the 10th/16th century, and it is noteworthy that *Jame'* does not include a single work in Arabic from that period, and only a very few Persian works.

Basic features of the program

Upon starting the program, the main window is opened (Pic. J1). In the upper part of the window, a Qur'ānic text is selected. In the lower part, a translation or commentary is selected.

Main menu

In *File* we find various matters regarding printing: (1) the choice of printer; (2) print preferences; (3) printing a verse (*āya*) from the Qur'ān, together with commentaries or translations; (4) the choice of translations or commentaries for printing.

In *View* we find: (1) opening to the Qur'ān/translation/commentary; (2) turning the audio on or off; (3) changing the view (choosing among individual *āyāt*, the entire text of the Qur'ān, or commentaries shown according to verse or page).

Search allows the user to search the entire text of the Qur'ān, choosing a particular word, or all words derived from a certain root. The user can also choose boundaries for a search: one way to do this is by indicating either Medinan or Meccan suras; another way is by choosing texts defined by particular boundaries (this is done by indicating the initial and final *sūra* or *āya*). Finally, the user can view the results of a search. The program does not allow for searches in the translations and commentaries.

Options provide the following: (1) choice of font (twelve in all are available) for displaying the text of the Qur'ān, as well as the translations and commentaries; (2) saving or loading preferences; and (3) choice of language of interface and information (English, Arabic or Persian).

Window provides functions for organizing the program windows. *Help* provides information about the program.

In the lower part of the main window we find the following icons (see Illustration 4, reading from right to left). (1) *Introduction* (Arabic *al-muqaddima*): this opens the introductory section of the commentary that has been selected. (2) *Comment* (Ar. *al-tawḍīḥ*, or in other words, “clarification” or “interpretation”). This provides exegesis for a selected verse (*āya*), from the selected *tafsīr*(s). (3) *Private* (Ar. *al-khāṣṣ*): interpretation of an individual verse. (4) *Common* (Ar. *al-mushtarak*): interpretation of a verse with reference to other verses that are similar in subject-matter, vocabulary or content. (5) *Public* (Ar. *al-‘āmm*): interpretation of

several verses that occur together, or in other words, of a block of Qur'ānic text from a particular *sūra*. This choice is made according to the boundaries chosen previously in *Search* (see above). These *Public*, *Common* and *Private* functions are activated only in the context of certain searches, and in certain other searches they are not available. The default is always *Comment*. (6-7) Arrows, enabling the user to proceed forward or backward. (8) The *Select* icon (Ar. *ikhtiyār al-tafsīr/al-tarjama*) opens a window for choosing commentaries and/or translations.